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NETWORK SECURITY MECHANISMS THROUGH OSI/ ISO NETWORK MODEL FOR UPPER LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

In this article the network security mechanisms used by host layers and the network layer of the OSI model are discussed. Many years ago, the existence of intruders was not established, therefore the security protocols of these layers were designed accordingly. But in present times, these protocols may not hold

much significance. Therefore it is needed that we either change them, or enhance them further. There are only few instructions available for secure programming and we have almost negligible resources for secure protocol designing. It is required to study the current solutions available and also for choosing some universally accepted Patterns.

KEYWORDS :network security mechanisms , secure programming , network protocols.

INTRODUCTION :

The issue of network security is a recent development. Earlier, the only question was about connection establishment. Internet was not so widely used and only certain set of people had access to the network. Therefore, there was no need to

design secure protocols felt. But with the increasing use of internet, where maximum data sharing, storing and retrieval is done through networks, it is of high priority to develop new and better network protocols. The purpose of this paper is to describe some security mechanisms which are used in network to application layer of OSI (open systems interconnection) model.

The types of attacks that can take place on TCP and ICMP are discussed below.

ATTACKS ON TRANSMISSION CONTROL PROTOCOLS–

Transmission control protocol/Internet Protocol is a widely used protocol for networking

.maximum of the networking applications use these protocols. [1] The error detection methods used by these protocol is highly evolved. It can adjust the speed by which network signals are sent. It is well tested. But this protocol is also not completely free of vulnerabilities. One of the most popular intrusion attacks is TCP hijacking. The headers of TCP carry sequence and acknowledgement number. The offset of the sequence number is set to the first byte of current TCP packet, which increases by the total size (length) of current packet. But, if synchronization (SYN) flag is set, sequence number is also set to the number of first byte in the current TCP session. The offset of sequence number is 1. Acknowledgement number is set using ACK flag, which reflects that the packet sent by the source with specified sequence number was received at the second terminal or the destination. This leads to a attack, called TCP/IP hijacking. First a TCP packet is sent from source A to destination B. Then, destination B sends an acknowledgement, stating that packet with the specified SEQ and ACK numbers has been received by the destination.

If an intrusion can be used to eardrop and the intruder is able to receive the whole packets, it can easily predict the next sequence and acknowledgement numbers. The attacker can now try to send a prepared TCP/IP packet to a victim with previously predicted sequence and acknowledgement numbers.

This can lead to following problems.

- 1) packet will be accepted and falsely processed by a receiving victim.
- 2) the real sender will now onwards send TCP/IP packets with wrong numbers, continuing with the falsely implemented sequence and acknowledge numbers.
- 3) ACK packets, sent by a victim will be thereafter not considered because of wrong acknowledgement numbers. New TCP connection is created by three-way handshake process. This is required for the process of fault control in TCP. Every TCP packet with SYN flag reserves some of its resources for a new connection. If a victim receives such packet, sends back SYN/ACK packet and waits for next ACK packet. If ACK packets not sent, resources are still blocked for new connection. This reservation of resources for new attacks leads to no free resources available and thus another type of attack called as "Denial of Service". This is SYN flooding attack.

2 METHODOLOGY AGAINST SUCH INTRUSION ATTACKS-

2.1 Based on transmission control protocol-

- 1) set initial sequence numbers (ISN) different than 1. The TCP protocol description suggests this 32-bit counter should be increased by a value of one in every four micro-seconds. [2]
- 2) use randomly generated initial sequence numbers which makes prediction harder. A very simple form of injecting an intrusion in TCP/IP packets is RST injecting. If the source is located and acknowledgment number is correct, the receiver will accept injected RST packet and reset the connection. It is very hard to prevent an RST attack.

2.2 Based on Internet Control Management Protocol-

This protocol is used in determining route of packet transfer from source to destination. This is very helpful but is also taken mis-advantage of. The most popular way of attack is "Denial of Service" [3]. Ping requests are continuously sent sequentially leading to a situation called ping flooding. The goal of ping flooding is to occupy whole victim's bandwidth so that it gets unavailable for any other services. Maximum length of ICMP data is 216 bytes. Several OS crash because of ICMP echo requests. Such attack is known as "Ping of Death" attack. DOS by ping flooding can be detected by border routers,

firewalls or IDS.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION-

Port scanning is a method for discovering network services. Every network service listens on specific port. These ports accept new connection. Every open port should response with SYN and ACK flags. After receiving an SYN/ACK packet, attacker should send ACK packet to finish three way Handshake mechanisms and then close the connection or just send the RST packet to tear down the connection immediately. RFC 793 defines some specific behavior of closed TCP ports [4]. According to this document, RST packet should be sent by closed ports as a response for FIN, Xmas or null packets. If a port is listening, RST packet will not be sent. if the attacker knows open port numbers, he can guess what kind of services are running.

CONCLUSION-

This paper describes only the most popular network interfaces and protocols used in network, transport, session, presentation and application layers of OSI/ISO model. We are still using insecure protocols. Insecure mechanisms of these protocols may be utilized by many potential attackers. It is needful to create new network protections. Many possible attacks can be eliminated by simple methods, like hard to predict random numbers, to use IPv6 with auto configuration etc.

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